

Mentoring

Start of Block: Intro

Q1 We are a team of computer science researchers investigating implicit/informal mentoring in open-source communities. Your input will help us identify implicit mentoring in open-source communities and understand how they impact projects.

This survey should take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete. The results of this survey will be used in a scientific publication. There will also be a question at the end of the survey for you to indicate if you would like to receive a copy of any publications or reports generated from this study. By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that your participation in the study is voluntary, you are at least 18 years of age, and that you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact

EEA Data Privacy: Participants in the EEA are advised that data privacy laws have not been deemed adequate by the European Commission. For more information, participants can contact

- I consent (4)
- I do not consent (5)

Skip To: End of Survey If We are a team of computer science researchers investigating implicit/informal mentoring in open-s... = I do not consent

End of Block: Intro

Start of Block: Block 3

Q2 How do you identify yourself?

- Woman (1)
 - Man (2)
 - Trans woman (3)
 - Trans man (4)
 - Gender variant / Non-conforming / Non-binary (5)
 - Prefer not to say (6)
 - Prefer to self-describe (please answer as comment) (7)
-

Q3 How long have you been involved with the Linux Foundation?

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - 1 to 2 years (2)
 - 3 to 5 years (3)
 - 6 to 10 years (4)
 - Over 10 years (5)
-

Q4 In which country do you currently reside?

▼ Afghanistan (1) ... Zimbabwe (1357)

Q5 What is your education level (or equivalent)?

- No formal education (1)
- High school (2)
- Technical training (3)
- Undergraduate degree (4)
- Master's degree (5)
- Ph.D (6)

End of Block: Block 3

Start of Block: Mentoring

Q6 Please identify which of these activities are a part of mentoring: (select all that apply)

- Giving/receiving suggestion with an explanation (7)
 - Giving/receiving instruction with an explanation (9)
 - Helping address an issue/error and giving an explanation (10)
 - None of above (12)
 - Others, please specify: (13)
-

Q7 Do you agree with the statement: Implicit / informal mentoring occurs in everyday development activities? (e.g., code review)

Agree (2)

Disagree (4)

Q8 Please identify where implicit mentoring takes place: (select all that apply)

Email (1)

In person (2)

Pull-request comments on GitHub (3)

Comments on Stack Overflow (4)

Comments on issues list (5)

Others, please specify: (6)

End of Block: Mentoring

Start of Block: Identification

Q9 Please indicate whether the following PR comments include (implicit) mentoring:

Q10 **Comment 1:** "Did you take note of the discussion on the dev mailing list? Would you mind going the extra step to update other tests that might be a problem (you're likely to run into them later as you continue with your implementation anyway)?"

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: spmallette)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q11 **Comment 2:** "I think changes like this need to be discussed before hand on the dev mailing list or on JIRA issue. This would configure a build on a Windows machine using GitHub actions. I don't think we need this, at least not in this form."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: zregvart)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q12 **Comment 3:** "I think this is better than reverting the three commits."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: aljoscha)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q13 **Comment 4:** "Thanks for this PR, but: Is this needed? Do 7 chars less per line change something? - It impacts lot of files for IMO rather very low value and could make regression analysis more complex knowing we have already changed a huge amount of code."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: pmouawad)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (22) _____

Not sure (23)

Q14

Comment 5: "Yeah, I don't know what things Kafka improve from Spark script so I wanted to see the benefit if you know about it. As I commented earlier, just adopting script doesn't work since we use different branch model (master, minor, bugfix) so it should be fully tested (including JIRA integration) before adopting."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: HeartSaVioR)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q15

Comment 6: "@swill @milamberspace weird, we've lost our Travis integration with PRs here. <https://travis-ci.org/apache/cloudstack/> says "The repository at apache/cloudstack was not found"

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: rhtyd)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q16

Comment 7: "ClassInfo#remove is fine, adding it to InvokerHelper#removeClass is probably fine too. Doing this to Eval is probably working out, since you rarely will create a class within the eval and then using meta programming on it. For the other three this is different, but adding a flushCaches we could have. Of course if we use Closeable, we could use close instead. Adding this to GroovyShell and GroovyScriptEngine would be actually a good idea I think. GroovyClassLoader is, because it is extending URLClassLoader, already closeable. So it could go there even without adding a new interface."

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: blackdrag)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

Q17

Comment 8: "This seems like it might not be backwards compatible with the existing kafka-spout; i.e., the offsets in ZK are presumably not going to be stored exactly the same as they were before. Is there any plan for supporting migration from the current kafka-spout to this one?"

--- GitHub Pull-request comment (user: erikdw)

Mentoring, why? (1) _____

Not mentoring, why? (2) _____

Not sure (3)

End of Block: Identification
